

Kinesthesia: An Interactive Voice Software for Intertextual Improvisation in Theatre Performance

Tilemachos Moussas

Laboratory of Music Acoustics
and Technology (LabMAT),
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens
tmoussas@minedu.gov.gr

Natalia Kotsani

School of Electrical
and Computer Engineering,
National Technical
University of Athens
nkotsani@corelab.ntua.gr

Anasatasia Georgaki

Laboratory of Music
Acoustics and Technology (LabMAT),
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens
georgaki@music.uoa.gr

ABSTRACT

We present a novel human-centered gestural system for vocal improvisation, “Kinesthesia”, to be used in new opera and musical theatre. We demonstrate the relationship between music composition, gesture and programming. An advantage of our system is the multimodal interaction technique through the invisible interface, which examines the use of electroacoustic techniques in human voice, in a theatre context. It explores the use of live or recorded, digitally processed voice as a sound source for the development of music cues for playback through a multi-channel speaker system. We also describe the application of the proposed system, in a real-time season theatre performance, where “Kinesthesia” was controlled through hand gestures from the actors, reinforcing the interactivity and highlighting the use of electroacoustic techniques in music theatre.

1. INTRODUCTION

Kinesthesia is a term that refers to bodily movement and perception. It is more specifically defined as, the sensation of bodily position, presence, or movement resulting chiefly from stimulation of sensory nerve endings in muscles, tendons, and joints [1]. Contemporary theatre is a deeply intertextual art form that weaves various performative elements within a narrative framework that is typically formed from existing cultural texts [2]. Intertextuality can be aesthetic, poetic and aleatoric, as it constitutes performance practices in creative performance. Performers display historical knowledge, situational competency, and sonify relations between them and their audience by bringing aspects of musical textuality into proximity through aural gestures. [3]

1.1 The Vocal Image in Post Dramatic Theatre

Nowadays one of the directions of music technology has been to increase the range of sound possibilities derived from the human voice and the level of efficient and flexible control over the voice. Specifically, the development

of computer audio processing has made real-time sound processing possible and the communication between the performer and the device responsible for the sound manipulation.

For us humans, voice is a primary means of communication and expression, while all animals use voice to express a wide range of emotions and inner feelings. Humans rely on both linguistic and paralinguistic utterance as forms of communication and expression [4]. Paralanguage refers to the non-phonemic properties of speech, such as speaking tempo, tone, volume, rhythm and vocal pitch [4]. The kinesthetic sense, although not one of the commonly acknowledged five senses, is the subtle regulator of the complicated body patterns. The interdependent relationship between the breathing and phonatory mechanisms is fostered by kinesthetic awareness. [1]

An important role in modern approaches to musical drama is played by the “vocal image” which is understood as the creation or presence of a vocal sound that is intended to form an acoustic image either connected to the language or independent of the language [5]. The actor’s resistance to a playful exploration of sound, in “non-language”, has its roots in the levels of logic that are inherent in language. This resistance undoubtedly inhibits a dimension of vocal creativity as well as the possible vocal access to the articulation of the various texts of the post-dramatic theater. The intertextuality of the voice refers to a dimension of sound play that is already evident in theater and experimental theater practices. Sound and consequently voice, are aesthetic features, capable of making tangible and relevant, an invisible and complex force.

Famous contemporary composers created seminal pieces of music using electronic apparatus. Improvisation has always been present in musical performances, as a natural extension of interpretation [6]. In musical improvisation, data are structured in real-time as performers invent and control parameters, composing the music “in vivo”. Improvisers follow the thread of their musically trained intuition into new and unknown musical contexts that the improviser might navigate in unexpected and novel ways.

1.2 The body as an instrument

According to Giorgio Agamben, “The gesture is communication of a communicability. It has precisely nothing to say because what it shows is the being-in-language of human

being as pure mediality” [7,8]. In other words: not only do gestures allow the body to talk without words, they also incorporate language; they embody language, and thus they are language and have a textual structure built into them. They communicate language, and they communicate by moving the body in space. The embodiment of language, and thus communicability would be nothing other than an incorporation of language into the human body [7].

In Greek ancient tragedy a highly formalised, anti-realistic acting technique utilises a pre-ordained vocabulary of gestures to indicate levels of emotional intensity. This language is based upon signs and not dependent upon words. A major characteristic of the Greek Drama is the exploitation of the full range of sounds, cries, and gestures, the use of facial masks, all these elements require the synthesis of artificial composition and creativity.

Through our research we approach the rich and complex ways that the voice acts inside the body but also outside the body of the speaker, when it is augmented in space during the performance. We study firstly the phonetic expression from the song’s structured prosodic speech and secondly the deconstruction of the speech through the voice for the expression of the instincts according to the paralinguistic code. Psychologists and linguists have demonstrated that a person’s voice pitch affects how others perceive her or him. [9] In our case A pitch shifter was used to reveal the performer’s state of mind: an unusually high pitch may reflect agitation or an unchanging pitch may become boring or monotonous, decreasing the listener’s span of attention. The pitch also could help the audience understand the performer’s social status. For example, a person in authority position uses a higher pitch than the one used by a subordinate. The other parameter we used is the volume since the performer adjusts the volume of his voice depending on the size of the audience. The larger the audience, the louder the voice should be. Volume variation makes the speech effective. Sometimes changing from loud to soft and from soft to loud will have the desired effect. Mixed signals occur when the tone, pitch and gestures of the performer do not match with the words he is speaking. This combination, in addition to the use of the reverse delay, deconstructs the text and creates a paralinguistic code which is used to assist in the expression and the reflection of the performer’s attitude. The result is a non-verbal material by nature which depends on voice, intonation, pitch, pause, volume, stress, gestures, and signals. Using our software the performer’s voice can convey enthusiasm, confidence, anxiety and also the performer’s mental state and temperament.

Kinesthesia can also extend the sonic palette via the exploration of non-human vocalisation. Spoken voice, shouts and singing voice produced by a vocalist are radically augmented in real-time by this custom interactive tool, giving the ability to the actor to create vocal soundscapes. Our aim is to expand and enrich the tools of both the drama actor, and the composer.

Plato called mimic arts those where the role of the artist is similar to a role of an instrument [10]. We focus in this “instrument” and how to increase its capabilities. The skillful

use of the body as a musical instrument is the source of fine reciting an singing and only through heightened kinesthetic awareness can vocal skills be achieved and refined [11, 12].

1.3 The Kinesthesis System

The motivation for developing Kinesthesia system, was the contribution in creating a new tool which converts the audience’s speaking voice to singing voice, used in the participatory music theatre (new opera) ”Oedipus”(2019), [13, 14]. Our system was used in a novel Theatre Documentary entitled “Kolokotronis’s Memoirs”. In this performance, the actor creates soundscapes with his voice and movements, but also improvises according to the dynamics of the moment, intervening and playing with space-time, thus sensually influencing the drama of the show and the listener himself, thus giving in each performance an unprecedented uniqueness. The concept of improvisation in the theatrical documentary suggests a non-essentialist approach to the concept of reality that is not restricted to mere representation. Therefore, the sound reveals the actions conversed and reshapes the linear narrative. There is a dramaturgy of sound, that rewrites another kind of text with the temporal and spatial dimension of acoustic events. [15] Also the voice is not merely as a means of speech, but an emotional, vibrant, gestural expression that transcends speech - and sound does not simply support music but is an autonomous stage building material.

The goal of creating Kinesthesia was to implement a system that could give the performer the ability to: (i) control and process her/his voice wirelessly , (ii) offer continuous automation in adjusting the parameters using gestures in space, (iii) handle all the integrated effects simultaneously (iv) provide multi-sensory stimuli to the audience through synesthesia

2. RELATED WORK

Twentieth-century performers pushed the limits of the voice’s expressivity through varied and often astounding extended vocal techniques. Sound poets challenged the equivalency of language and semantic meaning by using phonemes as abstract sound. Composers combined the expressive and the communicative elements with the emerging electronic technology to further explore the limits to this potential of the voice. [16].

Homer Dudley introduced the “channel vocoder” (voice coder) in 1939, which operates on the principle of deriving voice codes to re-create the speech which it analysed. In the analysis stage, the fundamental frequency is determined and spectral information is provided by ten filters. The synthesizer discriminates voiced-unvoiced speech by use of the energy of the fundamental frequency and generates a buzz for voiced sounds and random noise for the hiss. This signal gets filtered corresponding to the analysis. Flanagan and Golden have been extending this model by taking the short-time magnitude and phase spectra of the signal into account. Since then the now called “phase vocoder” has been developed in various ways [17].

Research related in designing interactive voice softwares

for performance, started in 1949 with Pierre Schaeffer [18] and his “Symphonie pour un homme seul” which comprises eleven movements using recordings of vocal and other bodily sounds produced by a man [19]. Because of the voice’s role as “primary expressive instrument”, composers and performers alike have been drawn to an exploration of its expressive possibilities on multiple levels. [20]. In Alvin Lucier’s work [21] “I am Sitting in a Room”, he records himself speaking in a room recursively until the voice finally becomes incomprehensible and what the listener hears are the remnants of the voice as excitation of space [21]. The use of speech in the work, with stuttering and swearing, provided Lucier with the natural anomaly contained in the rhythms of speech [22]. Laurie Anderson is famous for the use of the vocoder in her work “O Superman” [22]. She generates an androgynous, robot-like vocal quality by channelling her voice through a vocoder to alternate between male and female speaking and singing voices. In Anderson’s work “Stereo Songs for Steven Weed” [22], she creates a dialogue by turning her head between two microphones, controlling the placement of the voice in the stereo pair via her choice of microphone.

Pamela Z’s has a growing body of installation works using multi-channel sound and video, triggering the sampled sounds with the Body Synth MIDI controller [23]. Hildegard Westerkamp often uses her works to reflect on her own experiences and beliefs. Both of these aspects are present in MotherVoiceTalk [24] where she uses the technological capabilities of the studio to create a musical space where negotiations are made between private and public, the self and the other, and time and space, resulting in a work whose blurred boundaries, allowing the listener an opportunity to reflect on his or her own stories before they are only like a memory. Simon Emmerson was also interested in “extending the timbral world of the live performer’s voices and their acoustic instruments” [19]. In 1990 he created a work called Sentences for soprano and live electronics – the voice was processed live and distributed to the loudspeakers around the performance space. “If we consider vocal sounds, we refer here to the non-verbal, pre-linguistic possibly proto-linguistic exclamations: grunts, groans, moans, laughs, sighs, screams, and so on. These may express sadness, anger, awe, fear, satisfaction, humour and many other signals for sharing and communicating something about me or about the world” [25].

Donna Hewitt, is the inventor of the eMic [22], a sensor enhanced microphone stand for electronic music performance. By moving her body and the e-mic she distorts the sound waves, creating layers of music. Charmaine Lee’s music is predominantly improvised, favoring a uniquely personal approach to vocal expression concerned with spontaneity, playfulness, and risk-taking. Beyond extended vocal technique, Charmaine uses amplification, feedback, and microphones to augment and distort the voice [26].

J. Cecilia Wu introduced the Expressionist, a system designed for electroacoustic vocal performers, who want to explore the possibilities of using body movement to enrich musical expression [27]. Expressionist uses a two-handed magnetic motion sensing controller and an inter-

Figure 1. Kinesthesis’ Architecture

face that animates two- and three- dimensional interactive and dynamic environments that respond to hand motions captured by the 3D tracker. Laetitia Sonami, a sound artist, performer and composer, believes that the “novel gestural instruments have the potential to transform their creators” [28]. She developed the lady’s globe [28, 29] and performed with her creation from 1991 to 2016, before moving to an object-based interaction, the Spring Spyre, constructed using a steel ring and magnets.

The following works are using the kinect sensor in theatre performances. Schofield et al. created an augmented theatrical performance, called, Trigger Shift, following an 11-month long participatory design process with young participants [30]. Takatsu et al. implemented a system for supporting theatrical performances, that responds to speech and cues the next actor to speak [31] and Lycouris and Timmons introduced the ‘Haptic Experiments’ project which explores how blind dance audience members can experience the dynamic qualities of live dance performances through their sense of touch, using their hands [32].

3. ARCHITECTURE & IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Architecture

Kinesthesis augmented voice tool, is a gesture control tool consisting of, as shown in Figure 1, (i) a wireless microphone to capture the voice, (ii) an external sound card, (iii) a computer, and (ix) the Kinect Sensor v1¹. It collects gestural data in real-time and controls an audio processing patch, which converts human voice to an augmented musical instrument. The microphone-captured audio is used as a source material while an arm gesture provides a computational input that is deciphered and reconfigured to trigger the sounds and controlling the effects’ automation.

3.2 Sensor

The Microsoft Kinect sensor is a peripheral device that functions much like a webcam. However, in addition to providing an RGB image, it also provides a depth map. It is a Depth camera - Depth sensor. The library “open kinect for processing” was used in order to enable the Kinect

¹ In this implementation the Kinect 1414 was used, which is the original Kinect and works with the library documented on Processing 3.0 beta series.

e) Combinations of the above ways, so that a sentence begins vocally and ends verbally and vice versa. (It is also possible to switch from one type of recitation to another.)

The response of the system was immediate and efficient. The control of digital effects did not show any delays, and there were no problems during the implementation. The test was performed on a MAC OS X operating system, using a Shure Beta 58A microphone, an iConnectAUDIO4+ sound card and the Kinect V1.

6. THEATRE PERFORMANCE

Kinesthesia augmented vocal tool was applied in the interactive theatrical documentary “Kolokotronis Memoirs” in 2021 for 21 performances from 27th of July till the 16th of August and took place in the History Museum of National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Figure 4). “Kolokotronis Memoirs” is a research project, of the Laboratory of Music Acoustics and Technology (LabMAT) of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. The project was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.).

The stage narrative places the Greek general, Kolokotronis, a symbol of the Greek Revolution, in a peculiar, imaginary, historical museum, as a living and present “exhibit”. Focusing on the theatrical form of Kolokotronis’s speech, the play narrates his life and deeds, while at the same time the narrative is framed by soundscapes, live music, video art and live filming using digital technology, in a continuous dialogue between the historical past, memory and uptake into the present. Three actors and a musician (clarinet player), performed live. The main character, was creating soundscapes with his voice and his imposing hand gestures, using Kinesthesia, and creating a communication channel between the media in a heterotopic pursuit of history.

The protagonist, was enthusiastic using Kinesthesia system. It took him only several rehearsals to feel comfortable with it. His voice was captured by a lavalier wireless microphone. While he was a little bit insecure using the reverse delay effect, he was enjoying improvising with the pitch shifting and the change of the volume dynamics of his voice. However he was composing aleatoric soundscapes which were coming from an unfamiliar choreography created by his hand gestures. The performance was full house everyday and had great reviews, Kinesthesia transformed the actor to an interpreter of the acoustic memories of the Greek revolution, in a highly orchestrated way.

7. CONCLUSION

Performers need to be able to use the technology and to operate new tools without having any specialized technological knowledge. The tool we have developed is quite simple and unsophisticated in its use, when compared with other (previous mentioned) systems in interactive art, however, Kinesthesia is a versatile, robust, easy to assemble, low-cost tool that offers a new aesthetic approach for interactive sound dramaturgy in New Opera and immersive

Figure 4. Kinesthesia in Kolokotronis Performance

music theatre. Real time voice processing expands the expressive theater language, giving the director more tools to show the inner conflicts of the character, the opposing moments of action / thought, the memories, the worries, the desires.

“As the tongue speaketh to the ear, so the gesture speaketh to the eye” as Sir Francis Bacon said. [34]. Specifically, in gesture, sound can be used to represent a performer’s expressive movements in the same medium as the performed music, making relevant visual cues accessible through simultaneous auditory display. “As the tongue speaketh to the ear, so the gesture speaketh to the eye” Using Kinesthesia the performer “manipulates” the voice as material in real time, so that he/she is both a performer and a director and a composer. “An augmented or hyper instrument is an enhanced traditional instrument with various sensors to enable features of the gestural activity of performers to control augmentations of the existing instrumental sound” [35].

8. FUTURE WORK

The enrichment of Kinesthesia with more effects, harmonizers and predefined gestures, is under development. Also, a future extension of this work will be the incorporation of the Omax created by the IRCAM [36], so as to enable the actor to utilize live or pre-recorded material and to interact and co-improvise with the computer. Thus Kinesthesia will turn to be a media actor, itself.

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